

THE ROLE AND ROLE OF THE SCHOOL TEACHER IN EDUCATING THE PERFECT PERSON.

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Summary: This article discusses the importance and role of preschool pedagogy in the education of a well-developed personality, and discusses its age and psychological characteristics in the education of children. So, for education, what we've been given is the data of pedagogical psychology about the characteristics of the child, the laws of the psychological processes that go on in them. In the article, ethnography, folk pedagogy are mentioned separately in the system of linking other disciplines of pedagogy.

Key words: person, education, pre-school education, ethics, materialism, abstract thought.

The discipline of preschool pedagogy is closely linked to the social and human sciences. Pedagogy is the study of education as a social phenomenon, and is closely related to sociology, anatomy, physiology, psychology, general pedagogy, and philosophy.

Because these subjects determine the methodology of studying the goals and objectives of education. A materialistic philosophy of society allows for a reasoned approach to parenting. Historical materialism helps pedagogy to reveal the class essence of education, its emergence and development as a social phenomenon, the role of education in the life of society and the development of personality.

In the development of didactic issues, pedagogy is based on the theory of knowledge, in the teaching of moral education, pedagogy is based on the teaching of ethics about morality, in determining the purpose, ways and methods of aesthetic education, ethics is based on science.

Ethics provides theoretical foundations for ethics, deepens the understanding of the younger generation, the problems of its moral education, the role of moral ideas in the formation of human personality.. Aesthetics is the study of the general laws of the development of aesthetic relations of people to reality, art, serves as the scientific basis of moral education. Preschool pedagogy takes into account the age and psychological characteristics of the child.

So for pedagogy, it's important to look at what the pedagogical psychology has to say about the characteristics of the child, the patterns of psychological

processes that go on in the child.. So the relationship between pedagogy and psychology is very traditional.. Contemporary pedagogy is a multidisciplinary science, primarily related to the history of pedagogy in terms of the social phenomenon of education.. Ethnography, folk pedagogy have a special place in the system of linking pedagogy with other disciplines.

The general pedagogical group is divided into family pedagogy, preschool pedagogy, school pedagogy, pedagogy of vocational education, higher education pedagogy, special pedagogy, which justifies the peculiarity of the continuous educational process [4].

Education is one of the most complex forms of human cognitive activity, significantly accelerating individual psychic development and knowledge acquisition.. A teacher doesn't just impart knowledge in the learning process, but in this process, the learner, the student, is influenced, which makes them more active in their learning, so that the learner becomes an active participant in the learning process.

Theoretical knowledge that is instilled in the minds of students in the process of education is further strengthened through practical activities. A person learns the meaning of events, objects, and events around him by encountering them in the real world. It is only through practical activity that man learns the mysteries of the relations that constitute the process of social, productive activity, as well as the phenomena of nature.

As a result of interacting with objects, objects interact with the senses, and the senses generate perception. In practice, the active thought activity of a person occurs. Using reasoning , he deeply understands reality. When we talk about the importance of practice as a source of knowledge, we also need to emphasize the essence of the cognitive process. Knowledge is a complex dialectical process, a pathway from lively discussion to abstract thought and then to practice. Knowledge is the process of consciously perceiving the essence of things, events, and phenomena that are abstract and unknown to the individual. Knowing objective existence begins with perceiving it.

Perception is the real connection of the mind with the external world.. Perception is the mental representation of certain qualities, signs, or events of the world around us that affect our sense organs (we know there are five).. So every organ, every analyzer, I'm going to say,. P is.

As Pavlov pointed out, it feels some of the most important qualities of things. Perception leads to the conscious perception of the meaning of things

and events.. Perception is the process by which things and events that affect the mind through the senses are reflected in the mind as a whole [6].

Imagination occurs in the process of cognition through sensation and perception. Imagination is the trace of perception and perception that remains in the human mind for a long time. Or in other words, an imagination is a vivid emotional representation in the mind of things and events that once affected and perceived the sensory organs.

Through experience, you can expand your imagination. Imagination plays an important role in how we think, how we construct concepts.. Imagination is related to the existence of certain generalizations. Although perception, perception, and imagination are all important components of cognition, they don't completely solve the problem of knowing what is actually happening.. At the top of the learning curve.

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